

Effective Thinking Strategy: Five Elements to Facilitate Ideation

Aeron Zentner

The focus of this paper is to provide a framework to suggest that effective thinking is an essential element to the ideation and innovation process. The review of the case study found that a range of elements need to be established in order to support collaborative creativity. Though the aspects of diversity and professional expertise were present, the lack of core knowledge, unity of thought, communication, reflection and appreciation of failure and positive questioning led to the poor output of the team interaction. The paper also provided a foundation of recommendations for future research to build upon as means to determine the impact of effective thinking behaviors on the ideation process.

Keywords—Innovation, Ideation, Effective Thinking

I. INTRODUCTION

Innovation has become an essential element for organizations seeking to maintain competitiveness within the global marketplace. Berkun (2013) defined innovation as an outcome, which is positive change. The process to reach this state is outlined throughout academic literature with emphasis on settings, behaviors, and expectations. The impetus for facilitating innovation is through an ideation process to improve or advance and thus requires effective thinking. Effective thinking is not common practice, but an aggregation of various settings, skills, attributes, and actions that can lead to effective innovative and/or learning outcomes. Literature suggests that focused collaboration (Hagel, Seely, Brown, & Davison, 2010), emotional intelligence (Senge, 2009), participant awareness (Burger & Starbird, 2012), and a safe and open environment (Senge, 2009) can facilitate constructive ideation. However, reality indicates that these behavior are not fluid across all organizations, thus hindering the progression of institutional innovation. The following case study demonstrates how unproductive thinking can limit the planning and advancement of an institution.

II. SETTING

The setting was within a two-year, publically-funded higher educational institution. The ideation setting consisted of diverse department leaders, faculty, and staff members that carried competing interests for funding to aid in programmatic expansion. The purpose of the meeting was to formulate ideas and strategies to obtain a competitive federal funding for fostering new ideas leading to positive improvement within higher education.

III. FIVE ELEMENTS OF EFFECTIVE THINKING STRATEGY

The work of Burger and Starbird (2012) present behaviors of effective thinking through the five Greek elements of earth, fire, air, water, and quintessential. Though these behaviors do not take the physical form of the elements, they are represented

though a philosophical perspective, as means to describe the ideation process. The following section will provide an analysis of these factors to build a foundation for outlining an innovative idea.

This earth element represents a deep understanding of a situation, setting, and/or content. By building knowledge and establishing interest in a topic, individuals will feel more confident in participating in ideation sessions. Additionally, and building a common understanding of a topic will allow for smoother collaboration and can alleviate the time associated with building a foundational knowledge set. In this vein, as individuals collaborate knowledge with continue to mature through inter-group learning and thus facilitate a cohesive environment.

The fire element represents learning through failure and to embrace risk and reflection. Through the process of trial and failure is where innovation is birthed. Therefore, if leadership is seeking innovation and change, one must embrace and be supportive to an environment of informed risk taking.

The air element builds upon the depth of building greater understanding (earth) through continuous inquiry. Inquiry and evaluation should occur from inception throughout completion of the innovation process as these behaviors and actionize effective thinking. However, the strategy of questioning should be conducted in a manner that is affirming, complementary, and positively inquisitive to build upon and strengthen an idea. Therefore, this method can help shape the future outcomes from inquiring on the development and trial (fire) stages.

The water element represents the connection points of the deep understanding (earth), with the findings of the development process (fire), and inquiry (air) that leads to future collaboration. The flow of information (water) throughout the innovation process must carry an effective and timely movement which keeps all parties involve abreast in a manner that is clear and concise. This process is essential throughout all aspects of the other three elements as effective information as the results of each aspect can build upon one another to create a more comprehensive understanding and better inform the next steps within the innovation process.

The quintessential element is the actualization of the aggregate information and facilitates movement within a coalition. Therefore, the culture of an organization must be agile and trusting enough to move with the shifts in the learning and seminal ideation process (earth) throughout the development stage (fire), to the evaluation and inquiry process (air), and throughout the directive and knowledge sharing stages (water). Thus, in order to advance the ideation and process, organization

need to embrace learning and movement as a fluid and encompassing process.

IV. CASE STUDY FINDINGS

The observation of the group behavior rendered limited results as the focus of the participants was siloed in smaller impact projects and ideas that lost traction due to the lack of inclusiveness and ability to draw upon a broader spectrum of constituents to foster the plans. The following table provides an assessment of the unproductive thinking through the utilization of the Burger and Starbird (2012) five elements of productive thinking framework.

Table 1 *Assessment of unproductive thinking and recommendations for change*

Elements	Unproductive Thinking	Recommendation
Earth	Not understanding the parameters of the grant and the impact of building collaborative projects beyond departmental interests.	Review and outline the core information for the grant, review the current strengths of all departments and potential capacities to collaborate and develop an integrated model for positive change.
Fire	Not exploring why projects or failed not seeking an opportunity to change.	Reviewing previous initiatives, reflecting on the outcomes and refining the ideas that could lead to more successful outcomes. The process would emphasize using appreciative inquiry to celebrate the outcomes, and grow from the gaps that are uncovered.
Air	Not asking questions, practicing traditional strategies in silos, and becoming stagnant in the practices of normalcy.	Question why things are occurring similar to the 5 Why model of root cause analysis. Open the discussion for ideas to start, stop, and continue practices.
Water	No logical flow to ideas, which mirrored the spaghetti on the wall theory (Throw everything out and whatever sticks we can keep).	Work in diverse groups to address challenges and create focused ideas and based on leveraging collective knowledge. Record ideas and share information to keep all participant

engaged and aware of the discussion and findings.

Quintessential	Not thinking outside the box or wanting to change outside the current practices, but just adding to or expanding the current practices.	Embracing new ideas and being willing to and effectively executing change. Foster an agile environment that open to testing and evaluating new ideas.
----------------	---	---

Table 1 shows where the lack of communication fueled limited understanding and thus created a chaotic situation which limited the institutional-wide adoption of the project and hindered the innovation process. Additionally, the table outlines applicable recommendations that can be the framework for any organization seeking to advance their ideation and effective thinking process.

V. DISCUSSION

The focus of this paper was to provide a framework to suggest that effective thinking is an essential element to the ideation and innovation process. The review of the case study found that a range of elements need to be established in order to support collaborative creativity. Though the aspects of diversity and professional expertise were present, the lack of core knowledge, unity of thought, communication, reflection and appreciation of failure and positive questioning led to the poor output of the team interaction. The paper also provided a foundation of recommendations for future research to build upon as means to determine the impact of effective thinking behaviors on the ideation process.

References

- [1] Berkun, S. (2013). The Best Definition of Innovation. Retrieved from <http://scottberkun.com/2013/the-best-definition-of-innovation/>
- [2] Burger, E. B., & Starbird, M. (2012). The 5 elements of effective thinking. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- [3] Hagel, J. H., Seely Brown, J., & Davison, L. (2010). The power of pull; How small moves, smartly made, can set big things in motion. Philadelphia: Basic Books.
- [4] Senge, P. (2006). The fifth discipline: The art & practice of the learning organization. San Francisco: Currency Doubleday.